

A Study on Status of Education and Literacy in Tribals of Gujarat

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**Pruthvirajsinh A
Rathod**

Assistant Professor
Sociology
Government College
,Dhanpur, Gujrat, India

Abstract

This paper introduces the problem of education and literacy in tribal community of Gujarat. This paper provides review of literature, discussions and some data comparisons of various government schemes and budgeted allocations. It concludes with some remedies and suggestions how an Individual besides the government can improve education and literacy rates in tribal community.

Keywords Status of Education, Literacy, tribals in Gujarat etc.

Introduction

"Human beings understand that education is an unavoidable wealth, required to achieve the ideals of Peace, Liberty, and Social Justice, as well as to combat the challenges that lie ahead in the realm of the future." This is stated in the UNESCO study "Learning the Treasure Within" of the International Commission on Education for the Twenty-First Century, which describes education as an unavoidable goal. The Commission agrees that education must play a critical role in the development of both individuals and societies. Of course, the Commission considers that education is not a cure for all issues. Nonetheless, education has the potential to create the capacity for sustainable development in a harmonious environment.

In reality, impoverished groups, especially indigenous communities, must invest the most in developing these skills. This is a well-known knowledge that requires no more explanation. Education is critical for accelerating tribal social development. We attempted to debate on education among tribals and identified numerous constraints in its path.

Aim of study

Objective of this study are:

1. To study education and literacy status of tribals in Gujarat
2. To study various schemes related to education for tribals in Gujarat
3. To study budgeted allocation for education for tribals in Gujarat
4. To identify problems related to education of tribals in Gujarat
5. To provide for remedies for education of tribals in Gujarat

Review of Literature

Thakur (2009) :Tribal communities are regarded as among the most economically, socially, and physically disadvantaged groups. When compared to their male peers, women in these social groups experience the worst living conditions. It addressed the position of women, asserting that although people are two distinct human beings brought up in distinct genders, both are equally important, women are consistently treated as the weaker and secondary segment of society, necessitating a variety of means and measures to improve their status. Further thought needs to be given to this marginalized, oppressed, and disadvantaged group of people, especially tribal women.

Rani et al. (2011): The study on select Educational Statistics, published by the National Statistical Office, Ministry of Herd, Government of India, New Delhi, 2007, as well as university grants commission reports from New Delhi, Survey of India from 2001, and other sources were used to aggregate the data. It has been found that education helps women develop their sense of self, their capacity for independence, and their capacity for leadership.

Arya & Chauhan (2012): Tribal societies' perspective upon educational development ignores certain drawbacks that are unique to the tribal population. For instance, tribal regions have not benefited from the government's population and length norms as a result of their sparse population and sporadic residential patterns. Additionally, neither the tribal welfare nor education departments have ever developed programs or policies for tribal education due to the complex nature of tribal life and the expectations that tribal people have of the system.

Ashwini Deshpande & Smriti Sharma (2015) :This study has found a number of drawbacks in India, including caste and gender, which are both considered to be social stratification factors. Women and girls from lower caste groups are more likely to experience inequalities especially in education, this is one of many studies on how women have contributed to India's educational and economic growth. This study looked into the problems and barriers that women in India face. According to the report, major obstacles to empowerment and development include illiteracy, poverty, child marriage, and malnutrition.

V. Rajkumar Velusamy (2021) :Tribal people make up a significant portion of the population in India, but they remain far behind in terms of empowerment, employment, education, and other areas. The most important and crucial of these is education for tribal society. They need special consideration when receiving an elementary education. The national and state governments have recently placed a high priority on raising their educational standards. Researchers and academicians have focused a lot of their attention on the tribal people's educational accessibility and inequality. The outcome, however, falls far short of what was anticipated. Therefore, it is now important to give tribal education and inclusive growth serious consideration. The goal of the article was to use literature to investigate the current state and complex problems of tribal education in India.

Analysis

According to the 2001 census, the overall literacy rate is 64.8 percent, whereas it is 47.1 percent among schedule tribes. When all states and union territories are considered, Gujarat ranks 17th out of 35. However, Gujarat ranks 19th out of 30 states/UTs in terms of literacy rate among scheduled tribes. Thus, tribal communities in India as a whole, and in Gujarat State in particular, lag behind their counterparts in other States/UTs and other Gujarat communities. The literacy rate today is on the rise, but concurrently, the gap between the literacy rates of tribal people and non-tribal people is widening, which is quite worrying for all of us. The disparity is still as much as 22% even now. For instance, whereas the literacy rate for the general population in Gujarat reached 69.14 percent according to the 2001 census, the figure for tribal people was 47.74 percent, representing a significant gap of 21.40 percent.

Under the tribal development commissioner, there have been several additional and special arrangement for education in tribal areas. Since, 1953 Ashramshala scheme is functional, in 2020-21 70006 students benefited from Ashramshalas. 10113 students benefited from extended Ashramshalas. 8505 students benefited from Post Basic Schools. 3625 students benefited from Post Basic Higher Secondary Schools. Besides there are schemes of LLGRS, Adarsh Nivasi Shala (Model Schools), Eklavya Model School, Sainik School, etc. For residential facilities there is a scheme of Hostels (GIA) and Samaras Hostels. There is also innovative theme based schemes.

Decade	Total Population of the State (in lakhs)	Total Population of S.T.s (in lakhs)	Percentage with respect to people of the State	Literacy among general Population %	Literacy among S.T.s %	Difference rate between the two %
1961	206.33	27.54	13.35	30.45	11.69	18.76
1971	266.97	37.34	13.99	35.79	14.12	21.67
1981	340.86	48.49	14.23	43.70	21.10	22.54
1991	413.10	61.62	14.92	51.15	29.67	21.48
2001	506.71	74.81	14.76	69.4	47.74	21.40